

Social and Pedagogical Conditions for the Development of Homeschooling in Ukraine¹

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Introduction

The transformation of educational systems usually occurs under the influence of civilizational progress, including social changes, the needs of the job market, and cultural development. Nowadays, however, active transformations in the educational system of Ukraine are mostly taking place as a result of crises in the social, economic, and political fields.

The state system of education underwent significant changes due to the spread of the coronavirus. Adaptation to such realities prompted teachers to create appropriate conditions for schoolchildren's education to overcome barriers through the development of innovative models, forms, and technologies for the educational process.

Unfortunately, the outlined challenges did not lead to the culmination of crisis phenomena. They deepened even more with the Russian military invasion of Ukraine and the imposition of martial law throughout the country. The destruction of educational infrastructure, as well as the inability to provide secure conditions, once again emphasized the need to find forms and methods of education for schoolchildren that are more appropriate to the realities of the time.

1. Adaptation of the Educational Process to the Conditions of Martial Law in Ukraine

In the 2022-2023 academic year, traditional education was allowed only in relatively safe regions of Ukraine, and only if the school had a specially equipped shelter. As a result of the destruction of buildings and security considerations, a large number of schools were only able to provide distance learning. In turn, parents of schoolchildren, even in relatively safe regions with available shelters in educational institutions, did not allow their children to attend schools. Therefore, the format of traditional education stopped being uniform and pervasive. In the central and western regions, the majority of schools began to implement a model of blended education, which involves alternating online and offline classes. At the same time, the demand for distance education services significantly increased, even in these regions.

¹ Titles of articles, books, publishers, and other material, as well as quotations from these sources, are translated from Ukrainian, Polish, and other languages into English. The authors take full responsibility for the accuracy of these translations.

Among the main reasons for the refusal of Ukrainian parents to allow their children to participate in traditional education is the security threat. According to a survey by the Department of Education in Lviv, 76% of parents want their children to study offline (Shyyan). However, in general, the criteria for choosing the form of education by Ukrainian parents during the war have changed significantly. If earlier they were interested in the quality of education in the chosen school, what projects the children would work on there and how they would develop, today the acquisition of knowledge has ceased to be a priority. As previously mentioned, parents put safety in first place. The second place according to importance is the need for socialization, namely providing the opportunity for children to communicate with friends. In accordance, knowledge acquisition came in third place. The fourth place is occupied by 'care about parents,' which is provided by the school as a way of solving tasks that are largely the responsibility of parents. In the list of school services; parents are looking for opportunities for students to develop self-organization and cultivate innate characteristics and abilities, as well as to be able to concentrate and engage in associative and creative thinking and increase emotional balance. Online schools usually have such resources. They prevent psychological pressure and provide quality psychological support for post-traumatic stress disorder, war-related stress, bullying, COVID-19 concerns, and violence (Spivakovsky).

Distance education or e-learning has also been very actively chosen by families who were forced to change their place of residence within Ukraine (i.e., internally displaced persons) or those who moved abroad. Children whose parents are temporary migrants can use the educational services offered by foreign educational institutions. At the same time, these institutions try to support connections with the domestic system of education. The motivation to maintain contact with the domestic educational environment often comes from the difficulty of adapting to the conditions of the educational process in foreign schools, the inconsistency of educational programs, and/or future plans to return to Ukraine. Due to the state conditions, local governing bodies in education and the managers and teaching staff of general secondary educational institutions in the 2021-2022 academic year used maximum efforts to ensure the continuity of education in Ukraine, provide access to knowledge, and offer the opportunity for every participant in the educational process to learn, irrespective of their location.

The special order of the Department of Education in Ukraine stated,

In order to provide state guarantees in the 2022/2023 academic year to students of general secondary education who, under the legal regime of martial law in Ukraine, were forced to change their place of study and residence, have gone abroad, or are temporarily staying on occupied territories ... [it] was proposed to continue organizing the education of such children remotely or externally, including them as much as possible in the Ukrainian education system. Such students are provided with the opportunity to get an education in the general secondary educational institutions of Ukraine, including, if possible, in the place of previous education. Additionally, local governing bodies in the field of education may determine [the] separate educational institutions that will work with such children remotely or externally. For example, in each locality, there are institutions, which along with offline training, organize the educational process online. At the same time, students who receive their education online must be re-enrolled in these educational

institutions. (About Distance Learning of Students Who are Abroad, 16 August 2022)

Private distance schools offer a wide network of educational services in Ukraine in order to help parents who, for various reasons, want to provide their children with the opportunity to get an education online. Students can be completely transferred to such schools or use these schools' services to supplement the resources of other education forms. The popularity of distance schools is confirmed by their quantitative growth, as well as by the expansion and diversification of the educational services range. Nowadays, among the most popular services, the following might be noted: Optima, Dzherelo, 977, the Atmospherna School, the International Ukrainian School, Athens, and Unicorn School. The networking of these schools offers a variety of educational services, including online learning according to the standards, schedules, and educational components of secondary schools, as well as modified educational forms—for example, as externships or as free listener options.

It should be noted that until recently, regarding the choice of distance education options among Ukrainian parents, negative motivation prevailed. Most of the mentioned schools offer educational services focusing on the possibility of avoiding or correcting the negative experience of traditional education. Such schools position themselves as an environment “without stress, epidemics, quarantine, early morning rising, a dangerous road to school, heavy bags, overcrowded noisy classes, bullying and conflicts among children, etc.” (Distance School “Optima”).

At the same time, nowadays there is also a plane of positive motivation which is generated by safe homeschooling conditions. Parents choose such schools not to avoid something, but to a greater extent to gain something. Competition in the market for educational services encourages such schools to pay particular attention to the quality of educational services.

Among their advantages are barrier-free design, mobility for students, the availability of flexible schedules, time-saving opportunities, the chance for building one's own educational trajectory, a variety of forms of learning (individual, group, collective), wide opportunities for individualization of learning in terms of content and time, adjustment of tempo and the level of difficulty of the learning to the abilities of schoolchildren, externships, consideration of health conditions, individual educational needs, focus on interests, in-depth study of individual subjects, mastering of additional disciplines, interactive cooperation, unobstructed access to consulting services, constant pedagogical support, timely feedback, a huge database with various educational resources, didactic materials, and lesson recordings, among other features.

Such schools also provide wide opportunities for parents to be active participants in the learning process, so they can coordinate the tempo and directions of children's development, determine educational priorities, guide professional orientation, closely cooperate with teachers, receive timely and systematic information about children's progress, consult with psychologists about children's development, and receive other benefits.

It is obvious that the realization of all the mentioned advantages during the educational process in distance schools is impossible without the active participation of parents and their involvement in

decision-making and strengthening of the sense of responsibility for the quality of their child's education.

2. Social and Historical Features of the Introduction of Homeschooling in Ukraine in the Context of World Practice

Homeschooling has become another popular and highly demanded form of obtaining an education in Ukraine in the present difficult conditions. Parents can use this form of education completely independently, or combine it with the distance educational services of various schools described above.

The possibility of obtaining education at home, which is relatively new for Ukrainian practice, has a long history in foreign experience. In the United States, homeschooling emerged in the 1970s. In the 2005-2006 academic year, almost 2.2 million American students chose homeschooling as a form of education (Ray, 2011, p. 19). Quantitatively, homeschooling in the United States in 2012 covered almost 3% of all students, that is, around 1.5 million people (Noel, Stark, & Redford, 2016, p. 24). In 2014, in the United States of America, this form of education was used by 2.2 million children (Ray, 6 January 2015).

At present, homeschooling is developing very dynamically in many countries all over the world. For instance, interest in homeschooling has also grown in Great Britain, where all alternative forms of education are freely developing. This form is also becoming popular in Australia, Canada, France, Hungary, Japan, Kenya, Mexico, South Korea, and Thailand. Homeschooling is often popular among national minorities, because it provides an opportunity to resist national assimilation, creating the most favorable conditions for the preservation of ethnic and religious identity. Therefore, the goal in choosing homeschooling is to instill in children the values of the parent's culture, as opposed to raising children in the environment of a traditional multicultural school. Foreign researchers have proved that the ideological and cultural policy of homeschooling in the United States, from the 1970s to the present, considers the goal of homeschooling to be the "privatization of consciousness" (Sarajlic, 2019, p. 281).

In the United States, characteristics of homeschooling families have been identified in a scientific way: homeschooling is mostly chosen by families with many children, where the parents' education is slightly higher than average, and a quarter of all homeschooled children have at least one parent who is a teacher. Research has also shown a lack of correlation between the choice of homeschooling and a family's financial ability.

Despite the significant increase in the popularity of homeschooling in a large number of countries, there are also countries where it is not very popular or even prohibited. In several countries, homeschooling is illegal (for example, in Germany) or completely excluded, and can lead to the punishment of parents or be possible only with the permission of the authorities (for example, in the Netherlands, Greece, and Spain) (Budaichak, 2004, p. 51). In Germany, a special court has the right to partially or completely deprive parents of rights if they have deliberately kept their children from attending school (Spiegler, 2003, pp. 179–190). At the same time, information about anonymous homeschoolers appears in many countries, Germany included. Such trends create

significant difficulties for determining reliable statistical information regarding the development of this movement.

In general, in the most developed countries where homeschooling is practiced, and even provided financial support, the number of homeschoolers does not exceed 2-3% of the student population. In 2018, only 1% of children in Ukraine were homeschooled. In the same year, according to the results of a survey conducted by the GFK company for the educational platform “Educational Experiment,” society’s attitude towards this form of education was far from ambiguous. Specifically, 59% of Ukrainians did not know anything about homeschooling at all, and only 17% of citizens had a positive attitude toward the idea of educating children at home (Sytnyk, 2019). The increase in the popularity of homeschooling in Ukraine became significant in 2019. The number of homeschoolers exceeded 54 000 people, including more than 10 000 in the capital (Sytnyk, 2019). This distribution can be explained by a certain regularity in the introduction of innovations in the most progressive centers, as well as wider opportunities to supplement homeschooling with the services of distance schools.

We managed to collect data from 18 out of 24 regions of Ukraine (i.e., not the eastern regions, where hostilities are taking place) in order to analyze changes in the number of homeschooled students during January 2023.

According to data received in response to official requests from government authorities, the number of homeschooled children has increased significantly over the past year. This increase is definitely due to the war in Ukraine, the forced migration of families with children, and the destruction of the educational infrastructure. We combined the data obtained according to region—Western, Northern, Central and Southern parts of Ukraine—and highlight the results in Chart 1.

Chart 1. Statistical Data on the Number of Children Studying under the Family Form of Education (Homeschooling) in Ukraine. Group 1 (blue) includes western regions, group 2 (orange), northern regions, group 3 (grey) central regions, and group 4 (yellow), southern regions.

According to the received data, in group 1 the number of children studying at home increased by 15 times, in group 2 by 5 times, in group 3 by 13 times, and in group 4 by 10 times.

The development of homeschooling in Ukraine began with the implementation of individual forms of education. The regulatory and legal foundations of individual education were defined by the Regulation on Individual Learning in the System of General Secondary Education № 230, approved by order of the Ukrainian Ministry of Education on July 1, 1993. The purpose of individual education was formulated as a means of ensuring the conditions for obtaining general secondary education or satisfying other general educational requirement needs of the person, taking into account individual characteristics. The document stated that individual training is organized for persons who

- have expressed a desire to study individually (taking into account the wishes of parents or persons who are serving as guardians);
- have high academic abilities;
- cannot attend school due to health conditions;
- are unable to learn educational material on the basic level within the time limits set by the state.

(Regulation on Individual Education in the System of General Secondary Education, 1993).

Subsequently, on December 20, 2002, a new regulation on individual forms of education in secondary schools was approved. This provision contained the definition of individual education in the system of general secondary education as “one of the forms of organization of the educational process implemented to ensure the right of citizens to obtain a full general secondary education, taking into account individual abilities and skills, health condition, demographic situation, organization of their education in institutions” (Regulation on Individual Education in the System of General Secondary Education, 2002). In other words, the purpose of this form of education had acquired broader dimensions. If initially it was more aimed at creating conditions for the education of children with special needs, now it could cover much wider categories of education seekers.

In analyzing the factors that prompted parents to get excited about the idea of homeschooling in modern Ukrainian society, special attention should be paid to the growth of requests regarding the level of quality provided by educational services and the wider public coverage of various shortcomings of the traditional form of education. As a result of the outlined preconditions, an active public movement began in Ukraine in 2009 for the legalization of homeschooling and for its legal definition. Participants in this movement created an electronic petition named “About Granting Children the Right for Homeschooling in Ukraine” and started working on the relevant draft law. The authors of the petition stated that parents who are looking for an alternative to traditional education could not satisfy their requests, since there were no other educational offerings for Ukrainian children besides institutional ones. The only exception was studying in the form of an externship, which is provided only for certain categories of children. All the rest cannot independently choose an alternative option for obtaining an education. Thus, the right of citizens to education guaranteed by the Constitution of Ukraine was ensured only in the form of

compulsory acquisition exclusively in a predetermined manner, that is, in an institutional form. Therefore, according to the parents, it could no longer be considered a right, but rather an obligation, or “a significant limitation of the rights and freedoms of citizens” (Tolmachova, 2022).

Such critical beliefs about pedagogical theory and practice were advocated by many famous researchers. Radical views on the need to abandon school were substantiated in I. Illich's *Deschooling Society* (1971). In this work Illich insisted on replacing the school system with free education. Partly, in this context, homeschooling can be interpreted as involving a general rejection of school as a social institution, as well as intimating the possibility of creating a society without school.

Advocates of homeschooling claim that the main purpose of education is to ensure freedom. In their opinion, freedom can be achieved only under the conditions of homeschooling, because the entire environment of the school system is artificial. The conditions determining its functioning are under state control. It is irrevocably and systematically separated from the family, which is the most important foundation for the child. Institutional education is not capable of satisfying the basic goal of achieving freedom through education (Helios, 2014, p. 182).

The long process of promoting the idea of homeschooling and forming a positive public perception of it has achieved a positive result, which was reflected in the adoption of the Regulation on the Individual Form of Obtaining a Full General Secondary Education on February 3, 2016. Under this Regulation, the purpose of individual education was significantly changed and transformed. This was reflected in the definition of its new forms, which include externships, pedagogical patronages and familial forms of education or homeschooling (Regulation on the Individual Form of Obtaining a Full General Secondary Education, 2016).

The category of students who can choose such forms of education has significantly increased. In the beginning, the target group included students who could not attend school due to objective reasons, mostly physical limitations. Now this type of education was expanded to aim at covering the entire contingent of students whose parents expressed a corresponding desire for the alternative educational form.

Finally, the family form of education (homeschooling) was legally established by the Law on Education passed in Ukraine in 2017. In article 9 of this law, homeschooling was defined as “a way of organizing the educational process of children independently by their parents to obtain formal (pre-school, full general secondary) and/or non-formal education” (On Education, 2017).

In addition to the long-term legalization of homeschooling, the understanding of the essence of this educational form was transformed. In this interpretation of the idea, homeschooling could not be reduced to a superficial identification of its essence within the environment where it takes place, i.e., to a localization of the educational environment in the home. The understanding of homeschooling should be directed toward a complete rethinking of the essence of the educational environment. It is also important to clarify its difference from other forms of individual education, mainly pedagogical patronage. This form of education is aimed at providing educational services to children who cannot attend an educational institution due to their health. The family form of education (homeschooling) is mainly aimed at the formation of educational

services for healthy children, whose parents have determined that the most appropriate and effective option for the child's education is in the home environment.

In order to confirm the effectiveness of homeschooling, its supporters use a number of different qualitative and quantitative arguments. It is obvious that qualitative indicators such as a comfortable environment, the absence of violence, and a flexible schedule are difficult to interpret in statistical analyses. At the same time, an evident argument in favor of the success of this form of education is the results in student achievements that are accepted by independent experts—for example, in international student assessment programs such as PISA, TIMS, etc. The results obtained clearly demonstrate the high success rates of homeschooled children. American researchers also consistently confirm that children who were educated at home get 15-30% better results on tests than those who studied at school. Importantly, this trend applies to all fields of knowledge, in both the natural sciences and the humanities. Studies on the personal development and socialization of this category of student also show positive indicators. It can be stated that these students are at least well developed, or as well developed as those students who studied in public and private schools (Ray, 2011, p. 24).

Modern researchers have identified a list of the most important characteristics that parents note as advantages of homeschooling—characteristics pertaining to family values, safety, harmonious development, quality of education, flexibility and independence, religious and moral education of the child, and so on (Kucharska, 2014, p. 214). As mentioned earlier, quite often the motivation of parents is defined via negative terms such as opposition, refusal, or non-conformism. Nevertheless, nowadays more and more parents are guided by positive motivation, for example the desire for development, the creation of favorable conditions, and caring for the child's future.

Ukrainian parents scrupulously justify their position regarding the choice of homeschooling for their children. Summarizing several interviews of parents who decided to educate their children at home, it can be said that parents understand the advantages and disadvantages of educating a child at home. They often familiarize themselves with foreign experience in teaching children at home and make whole lists of pros and cons regarding such forms of education.

In an interview, Svitlana Kika—a manager and mother—said the following:

Even before the birth of my child, I wondered which school was better—an ordinary city school or a private specialized one. In each case there are pros and cons—the social environment, the quality of education, the number of students in the class, the workload, etc. At that time I did not think about the possibility of [my child] studying at home. Presently, knowing that in many countries of the world, parents have the right to educate their children at home, taking into account ... abilities, desires, and financial capabilities on their own or by hiring tutors, I consider homeschooling [to be] a worthy alternative to schools [in] the general secondary education system.

At home, the child receives an individual approach [and attends] classes according to an optimal schedule, [so] learning takes place taking into account the child's abilities (there is an opportunity to devote more time to more difficult material and not to slow down where the child understands the material faster) ... not [having] to adapt to others.

During homeschooling, parents can use various additional materials for learning (for example: computer programs, game forms of learning, etc.). Studying at home gives parents the opportunity to develop or support the child's desire for learning and researching, for the development of his personality and the real acquisition of knowledge.

The ability to organize learning according to one's own schedule [to make it] optimal for [the] individual needs of a child ... allows you to free up time for visiting sports sections, [joining] clubs, [taking] walks [and] interesting trips, and dedicat[ing] time for yourself. I consider another negative aspect of studying at school [to be] that a 7-or-8-year-old child has to carry a backpack on his or her shoulders almost every day, the weight of which damages the child's unformed spine. There is no such need during homeschooling. Of course, homeschooling should not replace education at school, because not all parents can devote enough time to it. Not everyone has the opportunity to hire tutors. But there are parents who can and want to teach their children at home—they deserve this right. (qtd. in Tolmachova, 2022)

Another interviewee—a teacher, a mother of two children—was Iryna Bilyk, who believes that choosing a school is always a lottery, a choice that cannot always be made correctly. Therefore, nowadays, the right to educate your child at home is very relevant. When asked “What is homeschooling, and why should it be available in Ukraine?” Bilyk said,

First of all, I want to draw your attention to the fact that some parents who have not studied this issue deeply believe that homeschooling is a kind of anarchy, and [that] when it is allowed, many irresponsible parents will simply leave their children without education, forcing them to work, or will allow [them] to lead a disorderly life. I want to emphasize that this is not so.

Homeschooling is chosen by parents who know what they are doing, and how [they are doing it].... [P]arents or hired teachers develop a study plan [for] their child. Homeschooling [requires] an individual study plan adapted [to] the school curriculum [and] approved by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine for study at schools. This is what makes it different from the general school curriculum. In order to teach your child at home, it is not necessary to have a pedagogical education. The most necessary [things] are the desire and organization of [the] parents. Certainly, you can involve tutors for help, which is practiced among average students, because the secondary school cannot organize full learning of [the] school programs [followed] by children in the conditions of crowded classes.

I want to emphasize the main point—homeschooling solves the problem of an individual approach to a child. Parents are not constrained by the time frame. They can teach the child a specific subject as long as the child [learns] the material fully. The second positive aspect of homeschooling is the study schedule. At school, as we know, this schedule is determined without taking into account the child's interests, but [according to] the work schedule of teachers and the availability of classrooms for

lessons. There is no such problem with homeschooling. The child has a place adapted for lessons.

The third positive aspect of homeschooling is the absence of conflict with the educational staff and the group of children [the students] are with. All of us are different and teachers cannot treat everyone equally well. Of course, they try to treat students with respect, but in the high-stress conditions of the school, this is not always achieved. The same can be said about the school class.... [T]he child who studies at home is not distracted from learning the subject. The child does not have pressure from classmates regarding various issues. The children who study at home choose their friends by themselves, not [from] a group dictated by the school.

The fourth positive aspect of homeschooling [involves] the individual lifestyle of [the] family. At present, many parents work at home or part-time, or do not work at all. Homeschooling gives the opportunity to choose the time of study: morning, evening, weekend.

And the fifth, the main important aspect of homeschooling, is the responsibility that parents want to bear personally for their children, without transferring it to the state, teachers, and society. Obviously, public and private educational institutions are good and traditional, but not all parents want to transfer the responsibility for education and upbringing to someone else. After all, they are responsible for the result.... I want to emphasize that parents choose homeschooling because it takes into account the individual interests and skills of their child. In Ukraine, all citizens have the right for education, but also we want the parents of all children to have the right to choose exactly how and where to receive this education. (qtd. in Tolmachova, 2022)

3. Organizational and Pedagogical Aspects of Homeschooling in Ukrainian Educational Practice

Despite the presence of a significant number of strong supporters of homeschooling, there are both skeptical and extremely negative social groups that oppose it. Some teachers—including representatives of the national institutional educational environment—are quite critical of the widespread interest in homeschooling. They explain the choice of homeschooling as providing a way for parents to escape the need to solve complex situations related to the difficulties of a child's adaptation to the conditions of an institutional educational environment. Parents cannot or do not want to solve the problem, so they try to avoid it. Educators are convinced that parents will eventually encounter this adaptation problem with children, but it may appear in a different perspective or on a smaller scale. So, first of all, it is important to understand why parents make a decision to take the child out of school or not to give him or her the opportunity to try to get an education in this way. "Homeschooling is not a remedy for psychological problems, not an injection for success. It is easier to take a child [into] homeschooling than to look for reasons why the student did not settle into the team. One might admit that there are children who cannot get along with their peers, for example, due to hyperactivity. But this does not mean that the best option for such a child is homeschooling" (Stepanenko, 29 July 2019).

It is clear that the opponents of homeschooling focus only on its negative aspects and are not disposed to accept the positive motivation of parents, which is based on the desire to receive more benefits for their children. Therefore, such discussion is predicted to last for a long time. The procedure of placing or transferring a child into homeschooling in Ukraine involves a number of organizational measures. For starters, the registration process takes place at the educational institution.

The first step to registration for homeschooling involves the submission by parents (or persons who replace them) of an application to the principal of the educational institution regarding the child's education according to the family form of education (i.e., homeschooling). Parents must volunteer this statement no later than 3 months before the annual assessment or State Final Attestation. It is clear that it is more logical to start a child studying in this form at the beginning of the school year, so it will be reported to the teachers who will immediately take this fact into account when organizing the educational process and preparing assessment.

In the text of the application, it must be highlighted that parents take full responsibility for the course and the results of the educational process, as well as that they will familiarize themselves with the rules of organizing the homeschooling process.

At the same time, the institution's administration is obliged to emphasize the great responsibility of the parents for the level of education of their children. Parents should understand this very clearly. Parents must organize the educational process in accordance with state educational standards. Moreover, the quality of student learning cannot be lower than these standards. Evaluation of study results and awarding of educational qualifications are carried out in accordance with legislation. Parents should follow certain standards which are defined in the relevant instructions. After accepting the application, the head of an educational institution prepares an order concerning the organization of the student's education according to the family form of education (or homeschooling).

It is necessary to include in the order the points regarding the parents' responsibility for the student's education at a level not lower than that of the state standards, and about the need for the parents to ensure the conditions for the child's education according to the family form. Under this order, it is also necessary to distribute the duties that are entrusted to the director of studies, who oversees the individual education of students and designates a social pedagogue, a class teacher, subject teachers, and other employees.

The rights and obligations of parents or persons who replace them involve the following types of activities:

- the choice of an educational institution from which pedagogical supervision of the child's homeschooling education will be carried out. As a rule, this is an educational institution territorially close to the student's place of residence. The student is also enrolled in the corresponding class of this institution;
- the submission of an application to the institution's administration regarding a request to enroll or transfer a student to homeschooling;

- the acceptance of responsibility for the quality of educational services and the educational success of the child in the conditions of homeschooling;
- the provision of appropriate conditions for the student to receive high-quality educational services and, accordingly, acquire knowledge at a level not lower than state standards;
- the involvement of additional subjects of educational activity to supplement educational services, which compensate for the limited opportunities of parents. These services can be concluded by students' parents on a contractual basis, both with individual teachers and with educational institutions, for example, private distance schools, etc.;
- the establishment of a portfolio in which the student's educational achievements are recorded;
- the arrangement of an agreement with the educational institution on the provision of educational services;
- the assurance of the participation of a student studying under the homeschooling model, and the assessment and evaluation of educational achievements in accordance with paragraph 6, 7 of section III of the "Regulation on the Individual Form of Obtaining General Secondary Education," approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine, January 12, 2016 (Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, "About Introduction of Changes to the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine," 2016);
- the extension of the homeschooling format, if the final results of assessment and/or attestation of the student meet the established requirements—that is, according to the indicators, if the student is not below the average level of success;
- the assurance that a student who is studying via homeschooling can be re-evaluated within a month (in the academic year) if need to do so is established based on the results of his educational achievements at the primary level;
- the creation of conditions to ensure an increase in the level of the student's educational achievements in order for the student to achieve appropriate performance indicators, to eliminate or correct learning deficiencies in order to transfer the child into study in the next class in the home form, or, in the case of a negative result, in the institutional format.

The school must provide students with the necessary educational literature, including all textbooks or manuals. Participants in homeschooling retain the right to use school infrastructure and resources: sports halls, swimming pools, laboratories, school museums, educational workshops, didactic materials, etc. Children also can, if they wish, participate in extracurricular school educational or upbringing activities: subject olympiads, clubs, competitions, holiday events, excursions, and so on. At the same level as other students, they are also provided with the right to celebrate their achievements—in particular, to be awarded with letters of commendation and diplomas, a gold medal "For high academic achievements" and/or a silver medal "For academic achievements" (About the Organization of Forms of Obtaining General Secondary Education, 20 August 2019).

In secondary education institutions, the organization of education is provided by the head teacher, the social pedagogue, the deputy head teacher, and the teachers. In addition to arranging the

organization of the child's education according to family form of education (homeschooling), the principal approves the schedule for evaluating the student's educational achievements and for consultations with the student and parents. The schedule is drawn up by the deputy head, who supervises the organization of the individual education of students and exercises general control over the state of the organization of the homeschooling of the student.

A social pedagogue or another person appointed by the school administration informs the Children's Affairs Service about students who will be educated at home. The deputy head, who deals with the problem of organizing the individual education of students, works with parents to inform them about their responsibilities and the requirements they must fulfill, defines the responsibilities of the teaching staff, and prepares relevant documentation. The deputy head must develop a schedule for evaluating the student's educational achievements and providing consultations, taking into account the requirements of paragraph 6, 7 of section III, paragraph 2 of section V of the Regulation on the Individual Form of Obtaining General Secondary Education (About Introduction of Changes to the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 10 July 2020).

These schedules must be agreed on with the parents of the student or persons who replace them. After this agreement on the basis of established schedules, the deputy head teacher organizes the assessment of the student's educational achievements in accordance with the established requirements, according to tasks prepared by teachers for evaluating the educational achievements of the student, and taking into account the expected learning results established by the educational program. The obtained performance indicators must be recorded in a timely manner in the accounting information and the class register.

Teachers are obliged to provide preliminary and current counseling to students, as well as, if necessary, to parents, according to a previously established schedule. All advisory activities are recorded in a special register. A very important part of the work of the teachers is the preparation of individual study plans for subjects, which must be agreed upon with the deputy head teacher. The concluded plans are handed over to the parents for processing.

The individual curriculum ensures the creation of an individual educational trajectory for the student, which is formulated taking into account his or her abilities, interests, needs, motivation, opportunities, and experience. Therefore, during the developing of the curriculum, it is beneficial to involve employees from the psychological service of the educational institution.

The following can be specified in the individual study plan:

- a list of study subjects (with a possible definition of the sequence of their mastery);
- the total amount of the study load and the number of hours per week for studying subjects, as well as the hours for electives, individual classes, and consultations;
- the schedule for the organization of the educational process, in which the following can be determined:

- a. the schedule of training sessions,
- b. the schedule of consultations,
- c. the educational tasks to be completed by the student of education,
- d. the manner of evaluation of educational achievements,
- e. the means of attestation,
- f. the establishment by the educational institution of a question list for the student through which the assessment will be carried out,
- g. the use of educational, sports, health, and other infrastructural materials of the educational institution, etc.

Such a schedule is drawn up taking into account the individual characteristics of the student's cognitive activity, and in compliance with state sanitary rules and regulations, the following are determined: first, the place for the training sessions, consultations, and evaluations, as well as the possibility of using distance learning technologies; and second, the rate of assimilation of the components of the educational program by the student (About the Organization of Forms of Obtaining General Secondary Education, 20 August 2019). At the same time, such a detailed determination of content and time frames may cause misunderstanding and resistance from parents. The most radical parents see this requirement exclusively as a plane of artificial restrictions on the individual development of their children (Botvinnik).

Actually, such parents advocate extremely pedocentric views, and consider giving the child unquestionable degrees of freedom regarding the choice of interests, rates of knowledge accumulation, forms of educational activities, etc. They perceive the establishment of clear deadlines for reporting extremely negatively.

Pedagogues cannot agree to such blurred boundaries to the content or timing of individual study plans, and try at least to issue an approximately structured and time-standardized form. In any case, on the Ministry of Education and Science website, the programs of all academic disciplines which must be mastered by students are published and certified to meet the established mandatory educational standards.

The process of monitoring and evaluating the success of students causes the greatest difficulties in providing homeschooling on the behalf of the school. Teachers are required to develop task packages for evaluating the student's acquired knowledge for the relevant period, taking into account the expected learning outcomes that were established in the educational program. The time and conditions for the evaluation must be consistent with the relevant sanitary and hygienic standards.

Appropriate cyclical reporting is provided for children who study in a family environment. Therefore, the final evaluation of the educational achievements of schoolchildren takes place for elementary school students (1 – 4 grades) no less than three times during the academic year, and that for high school students (5 – 11 [12] grades) at least four times a year. Also, in accordance with the requirements, students receive semester and annual grades. They also participate in certifications. According to the decision of the educational institution, the assessment of students' performance can be done individually or together with the rest of the students on the school

premises. Tasks for the final assessment are prepared by schoolteachers in accordance with the expected results prescribed by educational standards.

The formative and summative assessments of the educational achievements of elementary school students in homeschooling can take place with the joint participation of a pedagogical worker and of one of the parents, and be organized in an environment that is familiar to the student (Recommendations on the Organization of Individual Learning of Students in Institutions [of] General Secondary Education According to the Family Form of Education [Homeschooling]).

Actually, in practice this norm encounters most of its difficulties during implementation. Formative assessment of children of primary school age should take place in a psychologically comfortable and friendly atmosphere. A homeschooled child will understandably find it difficult to feel comfortable in an unfamiliar school environment. It is also very doubtful that teachers will agree to conduct the evaluation procedure at the student's home or in another environment that is familiar to the child, where any stressful situations can be avoided. Such reluctance will arise due to the fact that the time spent carrying out this control in a qualitative way is rather large, and individual load hours for such work are not provided for teachers. Therefore, it is more convenient for them if the children spend a long time in the place where the lessons occur, or, better, if their direct participation in controlled writing assignments is assessed. Therefore, it would be best to find a compromise solution that suits the teachers and meets the needs of the children, bearing in mind that their comfort and psychological safety will require considerable effort. The absence of individual recorded hours of teaching workload for pedagogues will cause them to have an understandable dissatisfaction with these additional duties. Moreover, not all educational institutions can attract additional resources to compensate for such labor costs.

Another problematic point, besides ensuring that the assessment procedure goes well, is agreeing on its frequency. As mentioned above, according to the norms established in the regulations on homeschooling, students' knowledge must meet state standards and must be monitored at least 4 times a year. However, as practice shows, this means that homeschoolers fall under conditions of increased control. The lack of systematic ongoing assessment prompts teachers to involve homeschoolers in a greater number of control activities than occur for students in residential schools.

Based on the results of the final control, a decision is made regarding the form of the students' further education. If the students have demonstrated results that are not below the average level, they can continue to be homeschooled. If their performance indicators in one or more subjects are within the initial level or below, or the students were absent when the assessment took place, they retain the right for re-evaluation during the next month.

At the same time, parents should make efforts to improve the children's academic performance, so students will demonstrate higher academic results. However, if the children's performance indicators do not improve even after that, by decision of the school's pedagogical council, the students may be offered the opportunity to exchange homeschooling for institutional education. It is not allowed for homeschooling to continue for those children who, according to the results of the assessment, have scored below the initial level of educational achievements. In addition, the school has the right to transfer information about the child's unsatisfactory achievements to the

Children's Affairs Service, which is entrusted with functions of guardianship. As a result, the Children's Affairs Service can conduct an inspection of the child's education and upbringing in the family, and of the parents' performance of their duties. Parents cannot ignore the evaluation or certifications of the child, since it is the state that is entrusted with the relevant functions of ensuring the right to education. Moreover, so-called unschooling is illegal in Ukraine.

The next plane of precedents is the problem of establishing relationships between teachers who carry out this assessment and students. Obviously, such activities require specific competencies which teachers may lack. Subjective non-acceptance of the form of education itself, negative psychological attitudes, and/or unwillingness to take into account the peculiarities of such students can affect the objectivity of the assessment, and the educational prospects and achievements of the students. In general, there is a rather biased attitude towards the quality of the educational processes used at home forms in the pedagogical environment of schools. Such mistrust can be explained by the rather certain novelty of this form of education and, accordingly, an increased skepticism may form about the ability of parents to provide qualitative educational services.

Moreover, pedagogical teams quite often do not have the desire, experience and/or sufficient methodical instructions to help establish and coordinate work with homeschoolers. The introduction of homeschooling requires, according to teachers, additional efforts and time spent developing evaluation or consultation. At the same time, teachers neglect the advantages associated with the reduction of the number of students in a class, the costs of serving students at school, and the possibilities of better organization of education for the rest of the students.

The new regulation on homeschooling also stipulates that the operation of so-called homeschools should be monitored by the Children's Service. The authority of this service has traditionally been associated with its working with families in crisis. As a result, parents question why homeschooled children are automatically equated with children from antisocial families. However, the level of responsibility of parents who have completely taken over the organization of the educational process and upbringing of their child at home is not commensurate with the level of responsibility of parents who have chosen an institutional form of education for their child. Thus, the interpretation of homeschooled students as potentially marginal or socially unreliable is at least incorrect. Such an understanding can only be explained by the current lack of appropriate structures or specialists in education management bodies who could perform correctly and effectively the relevant supervisory and control functions.

Among the other problems noted by parents of homeschooled students, there is also the problem of finances. After all, parents, as taxpayers, have the right to the education of their children using public funds. In the situation of homeschooling, however, they use only the components of educational control. For the education of such children, it is not necessary to spend budgetary funds on the maintenance of the premises or the course of educational process. Instead, parents believe that they have the right to redirect the saved funds to counseling services; that is, they seek to transfer these funds into the expansion of this network. Namely, they want to be able to turn to the teacher for additional professional subject consultation, if necessary, which is currently not regulated in any way.

The problem of accommodating students if they return to the school environment due to difficulties or to the impossibility of continuing education at home remains unsolved in the methodological, psychological, and pedagogical dimensions. In such situations, a special model of gradual adaptation of the child to the conditions of schooling is needed, because it is extremely difficult to overcome contrasting changes in the educational environment. It is necessary to clarify a system of measures and identify responsible persons who will help the child overcome adaptation difficulties, be they didactic, psychological, or social in nature.

In Western countries, where experience with homeschooling is much greater than it is in Ukraine, a system of assistance for homeschoolers has been created. It arose thanks to the efforts of parents who were engaged in homeschooling. In their activities, they turned to teachers for help and involved older children or guardians. As a result, various forms of cooperation, mutual support, and popularization of the effective achievements of homeschooling were established. Parents began to create various associations and unions, as well as new types of educational institutions, including associations, cooperatives, and charter schools.

Conclusion

So the formation and development of homeschooling in the regulatory, legal, and practical fields of Ukrainian education is taking place against the background of complex social and political processes. Homeschooling as a unique form of general secondary education is separated from the practice of individual education, and it was first legislated in 1993. Homeschooling was finally legalized via the Law of Ukraine “On Education” in 2017. The increase in the number of students pursuing this form of education has grown significantly in recent years due to the global pandemic of the coronavirus disease.

However, homeschooling gained most of its popularity as a result of the military actions resulting from the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine. The number of homeschoolers multiplied 11 times in Ukraine in 2022. To a large extent, the choice of homeschooling in modern Ukrainian conditions is determined by safety considerations for children living in Ukraine, as well as involving a form of belonging to the national education system for children who were forced to leave the Motherland but plan to return.

Today, there is an insufficient amount of appropriate pedagogical support and support for homeschoolers. There is a need to develop appropriate methodical literature to provide various recommendations for both teachers and parents. Among the most acute problems of homeschooling are the interactions between educational institutions, the direct interactions between teachers and parents and students, and the coordination of individual study plans and measures of control and evaluation in order to measure student success. The lack of experience in interaction with homeschoolers creates difficulties in ensuring quality conditions for the organization of homeschooling. At the same time, parents can use the services of remote private schools. It is likely that the increase in parent associations will lead to the development of special organizations that will work to support and popularize the ideas of homeschooling, spread positive achievements, work to avoid problems, and prevent the mistakes that sometimes occur.

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